

CONTAMINATION NAMES IN UZBEK ANTHOPONYMICS, THEIR FORMATION

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Abstract. *The article describes the characteristics of the names made by the contamination method in the system of Uzbek anthroponymics, the meaningful relationship of the parts of the names, their unique aspects that distinguish them from the names made by the simple method, and their linguistic features.*

Keywords: *anthroponyms, contamination, method of formation, double names, compound names, components, name patterns.*

INTRODUCTION

Anthroponyms and place names, which are considered to be a unique encyclopedia of the history and lifestyle of our people, are a priceless monument of the thinking of our ancestors, one of the great values that have enriched the treasury of Uzbek culture and spirituality for centuries. Therefore, we should thoroughly study and promote anthroponyms as one of the tools that define the scope of our national culture .

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS

In Uzbek linguistics, certain works have been carried out on the research of the system of proper names. In particular, to the work of collecting materials of Uzbek anthroponyms, researching lexical-spiritual properties, linguistic structure, ethnographic-motivational meanings of names, observing the specific aspects of Uzbek regional anthroponymy, spelling, explanatory of names Scientists such as E. Begmatov, N. Husanov, G'. Sattorov, S. Rahimov, I. Khudoinazarov, R. Khudoyberganov, S. Kenjayeva contributed to the field of dictionaries. Spelling and explanatory dictionaries of Uzbek names have been compiled. Despite this, issues such as the emergence and development of Uzbek anthroponyms, nominative features of names, motivational bases of naming, the role of linguistic and non-linguistic principles, scientific research of anthroponymy from a linguocultural point of view have not been studied without taking into account some small studies. .

Linguistic description, lexical-spiritual, comparative-historical, structural, typological-classificatory, sociolinguistic and linguistic-cultural methods of analysis were used to clarify the topic

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The methods of formation of anthroponyms are unique, and according to their expression, they are divided into such groups as formed from simple words, rounded and combined anthroponyms. The syntactic method of forming names is considered the most productive type of anthroponym formation, and the fact that 8194 out of 14600 are compound names and it was explained in the dictionary "O'zbek ismlari ma'nosi"(Meaning of Uzbek names) by E. Begmatov is a clear proof of this.

There have many investigative in Uzbek linguistics about the compound word, the semantic relationship between its components, the relation of the compound word to the lexeme

and word combination, the grammatical differences between them, and the methods of their formation.

The scientist E. Begmatov, who explained the emergence of anthroponyms in a double form, said: “Qo‘shma atoqli otlarni, jumladan, ismlarni yuzaga keltiradigan asos – bu kontekst (matn)dir. Bunda bolani nomlash jarayoni tushuniladi. Sodda ism ham, qo‘shma ism ham qisqa nomlash jarayonida tanlanadi yoki yaratiladi. Bunda nominatorning turli va murakkab motivlarga asoslanishi muhim rol o‘ynaydi” (The context (text) is the basis that creates compound names, including names. This includes the process of naming the child. Both the simple name and the distinguished name are chosen or created during the short naming process. This is where the nominee comes into play, based on diverse and complex motifs,) he explains.

Among the names there are also names that are close in phrases: *Xudoybergan*, *Tangriberdi*, *Kuntug‘mish*. But these names are also names that are suddenly invented in the process of naming a baby.

Among the compound appellatives from which the name is derived, there are also lexemes that originally had the character of a phrase: *Qizilgul*, *Atirgul*, *Oqbo‘ta*, *Oqbilak* etc. Before becoming a name, these names went through three processes: 1) the phrase "qizil gul "; 2) “qizilgul” is a compound word; 3) “Qizilgul” -name. In this case, the compound word “Qizilgul” was transferred to the function of a ready-made name without any formation, and this transition occurred suddenly due to the motive of beauty in the process of naming the child. Such names gradually entered the Udm and lived in the language as a name, and in the form of a ready-made name were kept in reserve in the fund of anthroponyms.

The names listed above differ from the names “*Melixon*”, “*Melimurod*”, “*Xolchuchuk*”, “*Xolniyoz*”. These names are not formed as simple words in the Uzbek language, but are unique names formed in the onomastic environment. With this in mind, compound names in the Uzbek language can be divided into two groups: 1) names formed from a similar lexeme that previously existed in the language in the form of a compound word; 2) compound names formed inside anthroponyms. Compound names formed from these two forms have long been used and formed in the language as personal names. The name for the child was chosen as a ready-made option among such names.

Although a compound anthroponym is considered as a whole lexeme, there are certain differences in the semantic relations between its constituent components. Accordingly, Uzbek compound names can be divided into two:

1. Compound names whose components are based on subordinating relationships.
2. Compound names, the components of which are equal and have no semantic connection.

The creation of names based on the subordination of components is based on the clarification of the semantic-syntactic relations of the parts that make up the name. Names with a subordinate component are made up of a compound word, the parts of which complement each other, explain, define. The mentioned relations arise from the initial syntactic nature of the formation of names, since the nominal components are subject to semantic dependence, and the name “o‘sib chiqqan bo‘ladi” (this means created in past) from a compound word based on the relation.

The composition of a compound name or the formation of a compound word is related to the characteristics of the name, such as the time of its appearance, the level of use, and the state of phonetic formation. As a result of these factors, the initial syntactic connection between the

components of the name gradually disappears and becomes invisible, turning into a single lexeme in the form of the name: For example, “Manguberdi”, “O‘rinbosar”, “Toshturg‘un”.

Polluting names based on subordination of parts:

1. Compound nouns of defining + defining component type	2. Compound nouns with suffixes	3. Possessive compound names
a) adjective+adjective relationship: Tozagul, Atirgul, Gulchehra, Sohibjamol.	a) additions with Arabic articles: -ul, -ash, -ad, -an, -ud, -in, -id. Karimulla, Sayfiddin, Jamoliddin, Asliddin, Aloviddin, Shamsiddin	a) Possessive compound names: Azizberdi, Esonkeldi, Haqberdi, Xolberdi
b) adjective – Xolqiz, Saribosh, Momoqiz, Mingnazar.	b) Persian-Tajik –i additions names :Baxriniso, Gulixandon, Zebiniso, Xurijamol	b) subject+noun verb: Xolchuchuk, Jonuzoq, Xolshakar, Umurzoq
c) demonstrative adjectives relationship: Oynur, Norgul, Xudoynazar, Gadoyniyoz.	5. Adjective + verb names	
4. objective+verb names	The second part of such complex nouns consists of forms denoting action, and the first part of the name defines the sign of the concept understood in the second part.	
The component in the first part is often in an incoming and sometimes in an outgoing agreement.: Izbosdi, Olloshukur, Tovoshar, Qo‘yboqar, Yo‘lbosar, O‘tbosar,	Comparative relation: Toshturdi, Po‘lattursin (Po‘latdek bo‘lib tursin)	Desire and goal relationship: Bektursin, Omonturdi, Esonturdi, Mingyashar
		Cause and condition relationship: Allabergan, Xushkeldi

(Note: the table was compiled based on the research data of E. Begmatov)

Double names with equal parts are closer to pairs of words than a compound word based on a subordinating relation: for example, : “Po‘lat-ali”, “Ro‘zi-tosh”

The formation of double names is a characteristic feature of the formation of an onomastic lexeme (visible noun), there is no semantic and grammatical connection between the components of this type of name, two independent components converge and create a single name. : “Jo‘raqo‘zi= Jo‘raqo‘zi”, “Xol-bozor= Xolbozor”.

Compound names differ from other types of compound names in terms of their pattern of formation. They are visible in:

a) the components of the double name consist of two independent names, there is no semantic connection between them: *Yunusali, Matmuso, Umarali*;

b) the value (symbol) expressed by the first component does not refer to the thing (event) expressed by the second component: *Oqniyoz, Shakarali, Oqmurod*;

c) the meaning understood from the second component does not belong to the concept of the first component: *Qurbonsuluv, Sherqobil, Qo‘ysuluv*;

d) the first component means a concept that has nothing to do with the concept in the second component: *Norpo‘lat, Norsoat, Pirqo‘zi, Nazirtosh, Norqo‘zi*;

e) the meaning of the second part of the name is opposite to the concept of the first part: *Sherqul, Sherqo 'zi, Temirqul*;

f) the action or concept in the first part of the name will not matter for the second part: *Turdibu, Turdimat, Tursunali*;

g) the meaning understood from the second part of the name associated with the birth of a child does not depend on the concept understood from the first part: *Tillaberdi, Oqberdi*;

h) the parts that make up the complex name are reminiscent of different creatures belonging to biological species: *Sherbo 'ta, Sherqo 'zi, Bo 'ribars, Barsbuqa*;

i) the components of the name express different and far from each other concepts: *Tursoat, Turdimuhammad, Tursunali*;

j) each of the components of the name is composed of a formal paired word, independent in itself: for example, "*Toshtemir (Tosh va Temir)*", "*Toshpo 'lat (Tosh va Po 'lat)*".

Paying particular attention to the motivational properties of names, S. Kenjayeva pays attention to the different aspects of double names and compound names:

Compound name	Double name
Keldixush	Tosh+Muhammad
Whole name , intact	Whole name

It seems that the components of a double name come together because they form a single name. The components of a compound noun are combined because they mean one thing together. In the compound name "Hushkeldi", a single motif means the gratitude of the parents for the birth of the child, two independent motifs are expressed in the double name - the child's soul will live as solid as a rock and the meaning that Muhammad (S.A.V) will protect him in his shelter. So, double names are names with a double motive.

According to M. Rahimov, S. Mominov, the motive (reason, basis) for the formation of a name is often forgotten over time. Especially, this phenomenon is often repeated in anthroponyms and toponyms with a combined structure: the formation of the name Muhammadjon as Mamajon, Matjon, the name of Shohrasul as Shorasul, and the toponym of Rafiqjon as Rafqan caused demotivation.

In general, two cases are observed in the process of anthroponymic nomination: 1) creation of a new, original name; 2) choosing a name from traditional names. The first case has been observed a lot in the past. This situation led to the creation of the anthroponymy system and foundation of the language and made possible the second situation. Now the process of creating a new name is not active, it has become a rare phenomenon: Erknura (Erkin and Nuryog'di), Mirshod (Mirzohid and Gulshod), Beknur (Bekzod and Nuriya), Nurhayot (Nurmamat and Gulhayo).

Conclusion

Compound nouns consist of two or more words combined to express a specific meaning and form a large part of anthroponyms. That is, the fact that more than 60 percent of the existing names fund are compound names is a proof that contamination names are more widely used than simple names.

The basis of the names made to wish the child happiness, good luck, bravery, courage, sustenance and wealth, prosperity is formed by ancient Turkish names, as well as lexemes borrowed from Arabic and Persian languages. It is especially evident in the names of animals and birds, which are symbols of strength and courage.

Therefore, each component in the composition of contamination names comes in a certain function and expresses wider meanings than the meaning of simple names.

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